

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D6.3 Dissemination and Communication activities v2.0

Document Summary Information

Start Date	01/01/2021	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.vital5g.eu		
Deliverable	D6.3 Dissemination and Communication activities v2.0		
Related Work Package	WP6	Related Task	T6.1
Contractual due date	30/06/2022	Actual submission date	V1.0 28/06/2022 V2.0 04/05/2023
Type	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Editor	Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS)		

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Revision history (including peer-reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	30/04/2022	0%	Initial Deliverable Structure	Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS)
V0.3	18/05/2022	20%	Deliverable Updates	Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS)
V0.4	26/05/2022	30%	Update Content – Section 3	Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), Nina Slamnik – Kriještorać (IMEC)
V0.6	10/06/2022	60%	Updated Content – Section 4	Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), Nina Slamnik – Kriještorać (IMEC)
V0.7	14/06/2022	75%	Updated Content – Sections 2, 3, 5	Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Giada Landi (NXW), Nina Slamnik – Kriještorać (IMEC), Juan Brenes (NXW), Athina Ropodi (INCE), Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), Cornelia Alexandru, Alexandru Vulpe, Gabriela Bucur (BEIA), George Suciu (BEIA), Razvan Bratulescu (BEIA), Andreea Bonea (ORO), Marius Iordache (ORO), Alexandru Oprea (ORO), Eva Tilborghs (DT)
V0.9	16/06/2022	99%	Updated Content – Sections 2, 3, 5	Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Giada Landi (NXW), Nina Slamnik – Kriještorać (IMEC), Juan Brenes (NXW), Athina Ropodi (INCE), Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), Cornelia Alexandru, Alexandru Vulpe, Gabriela Bucur (BEIA), George Suciu (BEIA), Razvan Bratulescu (BEIA), Andreea Bonea (ORO), Marius Iordache (ORO), Alexandru Oprea (ORO), Eva Tilborghs (DT)

V1.0	27/06/2022	100%	Final version after peer review	Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS)
V2.0	22/03/2023	100%	Final version after addressing comments from the reviewers	Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS)
V2.0	25/04/2023	100%	Peer-reviewed version amended ready for QA	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Makis Stamatelatos (DIA)
V2.0	04/05/2023	100%	Final version after peer review ready for submission	Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Eleni (Nelly) Giannopoulou (WINGS)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth-generation technology standard for broadband cellular networks
5G4CAM	5G for Connected and Automated Mobility
5GASP	5G Application & Services experimentation and certification Platform
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
ADMA	European ADvanced MANufacturing Support Centre
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALICE	Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe
ATG	ASOCIATIA TEHNOPOL - GALATI
BEIA	BEIA CONSULT INTERNATIONAL SRL
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DataPorts	Data Platform for the Cognitive Ports of the Future project
DHL	DHL EXEL SUPPLY CHAIN SPAIN SL
DIA	DIAKINISIS A.E APOTHIKEFSEISMETAFORES - SYSKEVASIES
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DT	DIGITTRANS
EAB	External Advisory Board
EBOS	eBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GA	Grant Agreement
GPS	Global Positioning System
HD	High Definition
HUBCAP	Digital Innovation HUBs and Collaborative Platform for Cyber-Physical Systems

Abbreviation / Term	Description
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IMEC	INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICROELECTRONICA CENTRUM
INCE	INCELLIGENT IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKIETAIREIA
INLE	INLECOM GROUP
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
MANO	Management and Orchestration
ML	Machine Learning
NAVROM	COMPANIA DE NAVIGATIE FLUVIALA ROMANA NAVROM SA
NXW	NEXTWORKS
ORO	ORANGE ROMANIA SA
OSM	Open-Source MANO
OTE	ORGANISMOS TILEPIKOINONION TIS ELLADOS OTE AE
PLANET	Progress towards Federated Logistics through the Integration of TEN-T into A Global Trade Network
PoA	Port of Antwerp
RC	Research Centre
SF	SEAFAR
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
T&L	Transport and Logistics
TB	Technical Board
TEL	TELENET GROUP
TEN-T	Rhine-Danube Trans-European Transport Network
TRA	Transport Research Area
UC	Use Case
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
VA	Vertical Agnostic
VET	Vocational Education and Training
VITAL-5G	Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

Abbreviation / Term	Description
VS	Vertical Service
WG	Work Group
WINGS	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE

Executive Summary

The VITAL-5G project's Communication and Dissemination Plan is a crucial part of its overall strategy to maximize its impact on the transport and logistics (T&L) sectors. This plan is being implemented under Work Package 6 'Dissemination, Communication & Standardization', which includes several tasks such as T6.1 'Dissemination & communication activities', T6.2 'Standardization contributions', T6.3 'Capacity building programme', and T6.4 '5G PPP collaboration activities'.

The first update on the actions foreseen in the Communication and Dissemination Plan builds on the activities described in T6.1 'Dissemination & communication activities' and provides an outcome of the dissemination and exploitation activities carried out between M6-M18 of the project. During this period, the main focus of the dissemination work was to inform the relevant stakeholders about the VITAL-5G project's vision and generate general interest in the project. The success of these actions is reflected in the evaluation of the communication channels used by the project.

While the VITAL-5G project has met many of its dissemination and communication (D&C) goals, the update highlights the need for further actions to maximize the project's impact and refine its D&C strategy to achieve the D&C plan envisioned. The deliverable identifies the strengths and weaknesses of the project's current D&C strategy and proposes a way to move forward.

VITAL-5G has already defined nine communication channels as relevant for the dissemination of the project's results in the scientific society and where the VITAL-5G team should be active:

- Workshops,
- Hackathon,
- Conferences,
- Newsletters,
- Industry professional events,
- Videos,
- Press releases,
- Scientific publications, and,
- Social Media: LinkedIn and Twitter being the main avenues.

One of the critical steps taken to improve the project's impact is the formation of an External Advisory Board, whose first meeting is detailed in the deliverable. The Board's role and recruitment process are presented, and the meeting is deemed a success. The External Advisory Board is expected to play a crucial role in helping the project maximize its outreach to the target audiences and its impact on the T&L sectors.

1 Introduction

The VITAL-5G project aims at advancing offered transport & logistics (T&L) services by engaging significant logistics stakeholders (sea and river port authorities, road logistics operators, warehouse/hub logistic operators), as well as innovative SMEs and offering them an open and secure virtualized 5G environment to test, validate and verify T&L related cutting-edge Network Applications.

Due to the numerous technological novelties and their applications produced by the VITAL-5G project, their dissemination to the maximum number of relevant stakeholders is a key factor for the project's success. The dissemination of the developed ideas and the obtained results to a wide audience, ranging from the research community to relevant industries and general audiences, is critical for the overall success and the impact of VITAL-5G on the society. To that end, a set of tools has been created to promote the VITAL-5G solutions both to expert and non-expert audience.

This report is the second of a series of three consecutive deliverables related to the D&C activities of the project and provides the interim dissemination and communication strategy of VITAL-5G. D6.3 as the interim report describes the results from the outreach activities by giving a comprehensive evaluation and impact status. It describes the different collaborations with other research projects, liaison with innovation stakeholders, the organization activities of the VITAL-5G Hackathon, the engagement activities of 3rd-parties, how the external advisory board was completed and how will help the progress of the project. Finally, a thorough description is given for the D&C goals until the completion of VITAL-5G project.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 6.1 Dissemination & communication activities	This task will define the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) plans and select appropriate tools to be used by the consortium for internal/external communication. The main elements of the D&C plan will be tasks, responsible partners, materials used, audience addressed and timing.	Chapter 2 Chapter 3	We describe our Dissemination and Exploitation strategy and what has been achieved so far. Furthermore, we evaluate the dissemination and communication tools we have at our disposal.
	The project's intermediate results will also be presented in form of white papers, presentations and online	Chapter 2	We report the 5G-PPP whitepapers that VITAL-5G has been a part of and the participation to various industry and

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<p>demos in various conferences and industrial exhibitions with the purpose of commercially exploiting the project's results and identifying new partners for collaboration in the EU market.</p>		<p>academic events that the project has participated in.</p>
	<p>The following options will also be considered: (i) joint organization with other relevant 5G PPP projects, (ii) co-hosting in the framework of other well-established events, (iii) organization of a session with other 5G stakeholders, (iv) cooperation with 5G PPP WGs and mapping of results.</p>	<p>Chapter 2</p>	<p>We report the active participation of VITAL-5G members to 5G-PPP WG and the collaborations forged with other 5G T&L projects.</p>
	<p>The portal will be complemented by a social media communication strategy and channels (e.g., LinkedIn groups, Facebook) that will ensure a broad diffusion of the project results and promote the project in online discussion communities.</p>	<p>Chapter 2</p>	<p>We provide an update regarding the social media communication strategy and provide metrics.</p>
<p>Task 6.3 Capacity building programme</p>	<p>Besides the interaction with other projects, this task will also lead the interaction with relevant stakeholders and will assist in the discovery, training and general interaction with the 3rd party experimenters.</p>	<p>Chapter 4</p>	<p>We provide the description of the preparation and initiation of the 3rd party experimenters activities.</p>
DELIVERABLE			
D6.3 Dissemination and Communication activities v2.0			

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
Intermediate version of the dissemination and communication plan and report containing the dissemination and communication activities implemented.			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The D&C strategy laid out for the project is carefully designed to follow a D&C plan that will be monitored for the duration of the project. The communication plan is presented, emphasizing the various digital and non-digital communication channels in use, and the overall action plan developed for efficient communication of the project to all the relative stakeholders, aiming at maximum impact.

Similarly, the dissemination plan includes all the appropriate dissemination means that are being utilized for efficiently transmitting the results and the technological advances of the project to the corresponding scientific, academic, research, industrial and general public target audiences.

A section is dedicated specifically to 3rd party engagement activities and how we are approaching the targeted audiences in order to offer the project's assets for experimentation thus creating a VITAL-5G ecosystem and exploiting further the results of the project.

After describing the External Advisory Board, the recruitment procedure, its role and the first meeting that took place in March 2022, the future D&C goals are described which will be reported in the final report in the form of D6.4.

To aid this narrative, the deliverable is split into the following chapters:

- **Chapter 2** deals with the report on dissemination and communication activities,
- **Chapter 3** describes the efforts of VITAL-5G to connect with innovation stakeholders through various activities,
- **Chapter 4** deals with the 3rd party engagement activities,
- **Chapter 5** describes the recruitment and first actions of the External Advisory Board of VITAL-5G, and,
- **Chapter 6** sets the D&C goals for the remainder of the project.

2 VITAL-5G Dissemination and Communication Report (M6-M18)

A comprehensive set of dedicated dissemination, communication and community building activities are contributing to the overall success of VITAL-5G. The main goal of the VITAL-5G D&C strategy is to create and spread the awareness of the project and its results to the broadest possible audience and to attract potential users and customers.

To reach this goal, VITAL-5G differentiates between two major strands of communication: i) the general communication activities, which are being focused on, mainly between M6 – M18 of the project, targeting the wide public audience, and, ii) a set of more dedicated dissemination activities, designed to present VITAL-5G's advances and outcomes to the scientific communities, academia, targeted SMEs, relevant industries, 3rd parties and end-users. This type of communication is becoming more important as the project evolves, and concrete results are the focus of the dissemination plan.

2.1 Outreach activities of VITAL-5G Project

The outreach activities of VITAL-5G Project can be categorized into three main areas: (i) scientific activities by publishing in peer-review journals and presenting in conferences, (ii) capacity building activities such as workshops and collaboration with other research projects, and (iii) broad communication activities.

2.1.1 Scientific Publications and Conference Proceedings

The VITAL-5G project is active in world-class scientific conferences for 5G technology (e.g., EuCNC & 6G Summit)¹ and the relevant 5G PPP communities. The project at the moment of the submission of the deliverable has the publications set to be published as shown in Table 2:

Table 2: Scientific Publications and Conference Proceedings submitted.

Title	Journal/Conference	Status	VITAL-5G partners	Full Reference
VITAL-5G: A novel 5G-enabled platform for Vertical Innovations in Transport and Logistics	Transportation Research Procedia	To be presented at the Transport Research Arena (TRA) 2022 Conference	EBOS, IMEC, DT, BEIA, ORO, NXW, WINGS	VITAL-5G: A novel 5G-enabled platform for Vertical Innovations in Transport and Logistics , <i>Andreas Kartakoullis, Nina Slamnik-Kriještovac, Valentin Carlanç, Alexandru Vulpe, George Suciu, Marius Iordache, Juan Brenes, Giada Landi, Konstantinos Trichias</i> , Transportation Research Procedia
Network Applications (NetApps) as a 5G booster for T&L Services: The VITAL-5G approach	2022 EuCNC & 6G Summit	Presented at the 2022 EuCNC & 6G Summit	NXW, BEIA, DT, WINGS, INCE	Network Applications (NetApps) as a 5G Booster for Transport & Logistics (T&L) Services: The VITAL-5G Approach , <i>Nina Slamnik-Krijestovac; Giada Landi; Juan Brenes; Alexandru Vulpe; George</i>

¹ <https://www.eucnc.eu/>

Title	Journal/Conference	Status	VITAL-5G partners	Full Reference
				<i>Suciu; Valentin Carlan; Konstantinos Trichias; Ilias Kotinas; Esteban Municio; Athina Ropodi; Johann M. Marquez-Barja</i>

It is worth noting that in this deliverable we report on publications that are conceptualized after the period covered by D6.2. Apart from scientific publications and conference proceedings, VITAL-5G has actively participated in publications of white papers in the context of 5G-PPP. A comprehensive list of the VITAL-5G contributions in the white papers is described in D6.8.

An important milestone of the project is our incorporation into the OSM ecosystem. VITAL-5G has received the OSM-Ecosystem – Research Badge and is now included in the official OSM WikiHub². The badge can be used in every dissemination material in combination with the VITAL-5G logo.

Figure 1: OSM-Ecosystem - Research Badge (Left) and official tweet by OSM declaring that the VITAL-5G project is part of the OSM Ecosystem.

2.1.2 Workshops, Webinars and Collaborations with other Horizon 2020 Projects

The first webinar of VITAL-5G took place on the 5th of April 2022 and it was extensively advertised from the social media of the project. A specific invitation (see Figure 2) and an online event on Eventbrite was created for the webinar “5G Network Applications for Transport & Logistic services: Concepts, modelling and practical examples”³. In total, **50 tickets** were distributed through the Eventbrite platform for this webinar with **441 page views**. Even though the number of attendees was low relative to the consortium size, we used the opportunity to learn on how to properly engage audiences and organise such events including that a more successful campaign needs to be launched in an expanded timeframe to attract all relevant stakeholders.

² <https://osm.etsi.org/wikipub/index.php/Research#Vital-5G>

³ <https://www.eventbrite.com/e/5g-netapps-for-transport-logistic-services-tickets-299136474247>

The webinar was separated into three different small talks that were presented by Giada Landi (Nextworks, Italy) “VITAL-5G Network Applications modelling and experimentation”, Nina Slamnik-Krijestorac (IMEC, Belgium) “An example of Vertical Agnostic Network Application: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation” and Dr. Alexandru Vulpe “An example of Vertical Specific Network Application: On board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II”.

VITAL 5G "5G NetApps for Transport & Logistic services: concepts, modelling and practical examples"

1500 CET, Tuesday 5th of April 2022

Giada Landi,
Nextworks (IT)

Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac,
imec (BE)

Dr. Alexandru Vulpe,
BEIA (RO)

Scan here to join the meeting:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016567. For more information: www.vital5g.eu

Figure 2: The invitation of the first VITAL-5G webinar.

As part of the WP6 outreach activities, VITAL-5G has initiated a number of synergies with other T&L Horizon 2020 projects that are covering different aspects of the T&L sector. More specifically, two synergies with the Horizon 2020 projects **Progress towards Federated Logistics through the Integration of TEN-T into A Global Trade Network (PLANET)**⁴ and **DataPorts – Data Platform for the Cognitive Ports of the Future**⁵ are described in detail in D6.8.

In addition to PLANET and Dataports synergies, VITAL-5G also participated in the **launch of the ALICE 5G Interest Group** (Figure 3). The objective of the focus group will be the identification of projects utilizing the 5G technology that relate to T&L, the collection of information for 5G logistics applications, liaison with as many of them as possible, presentation of their results and maturity levels to the members of the thematic group and evaluation of how they align with ALICE PI roadmap⁶.

The purpose of our participation is to connect with T&L oriented projects and promote our services and assets as well as increasing the visibility of our project.

⁴ <https://www.planetproject.eu/>

⁵ <https://dataports-project.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.etp-logistics.eu/alice-physical-internet-roadmap-released/>

Figure 3: The invitation to the launch of the ALICE 5G Interest Group.

VITAL-5G participated in the **5G NetApp Lab Launch Event** (Figure 4) which was performed under the hospices of the 5GASP Network Application community⁷. 5G Network Application Lab supports start-ups, SMEs, developers and researchers that wish to design and deliver valuable 5G products and services, leveraging the native 5G technology capabilities. In the event VITAL-5G presented its ecosystem through its ORO representatives.

Figure 4: Invitation for the 5GNetApp Lab event.

The project's coordinator, Kostas Trichias, participated in the **special session in the 2022 EuCNC & 6G Summit "NetApps for Verticals"** which focused on discussing how Network Application empowers the verticals on-boarding on 5G. VITAL-5G is an actor from the T&L vertical domain and thus its input was invaluable for this session.

2.1.3 Press Releases and Newsletters

The Newsletter and Press Releases are an important component of the communication strategy as they are used to diffuse the latest news and achievements at regular intervals to the wider public and the different stakeholders. The objective is to keep the community informed and engaged with the project and achieve more visibility and credibility. The second press release (Figure 5) is completed by DHL and EBOS.

⁷ <https://community.5gasp.eu/index.php/NetworkApplicationlab/>

Furthermore, the second newsletter of the project was created (see Figure 6) and distributed through the mailing lists of the project.

Figure 5: Second VITAL-5G press release by EBOS and DHL.

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

CONSORTIUM

WINGS, Bela, DASHNET, BOS, etc.

Overview

As 5G networks are being deployed across the world, more and more vertical industries are discovering the benefits of 5G connectivity and the opportunities and innovation models that it has to offer. The Transport & Logistics (T&L) industry is a vertical sector that is expected to be one of the key adopters of 5G technology. However, the adoption and penetration of 5G-based solutions in T&L may be hindered by the knowledge/experience gap between the vertical industry, the telecommunications experts and the application developers.

The VITAL-5G project has the vision to advance the offered T&L services by engaging significant logistics stakeholders. Do not forget our activities, need logistics operators, warehouse/fulfillment operations, etc. as well as innovative 5G/L4 and autonomous solutions, and allowing them to validate their T&L-related solutions, and ensuring ongoing positive responses and advanced 5G activities.

To support both internal and 3rd-party experimentation, VITAL-5G will create an open, flexible and secure virtualized 5G experimentation facility to enable the testing and validation of T&L-related cutting-edge Network Applications (NetApps) utilizing 5G connectivity.

Sixteen partners from 6 countries, including 3 major European T&L operators, 3 leading European T&L providers and a strong leader of 3 innovation SMEs, will address multiple use cases in the area of 5G enabled warehouse/fulfillment operations, remote logistics operations, vessel automation and data-enabled access/navigation for ports.

VITAL-5G Dissemination Activities

5G NetApps for Transport & Logistics Services, concepts and practical examples

The first webinar of VITAL-5G "5G NetApps for Transport & Logistics" services, concepts and practical examples" is available on our YouTube channel. In this webinar, we presented how 5G-enabled NetApps can become a key enabler in the digital transformation of the T&L sector. NetApps can abstract the complexity of the underlying 5G infrastructure in T&L application developers, significantly reduce the service creation and deployment times, and optimize the utilization of 5G resources thus leading to reduced service deployment costs.

InfoCom World 2021 - Recharging Greece: Revolution of the Evolvent!

Mrs Christina Lelou from OTE Laboratories for Technology Development and Innovation presented the VITAL-5G use cases at the InfoCom World 2021 Recharging Greece. Revolution of the Evolvent!

The objective of the conference was to "give the mic" to those with solutions and proposals to present, in order to accelerate the pace of digital development, as well as to promote creative discussions.

IEEE International Symposium on Signals, Circuits and Systems (ISSCS)

VITAL-5G project partner Orange Romania participated with two papers in the IEEE International Symposium on Signals, Circuits and Systems with two papers:

"Automated Onboarding, Testing and Validation Framework for NetApps" and "Evaluation of electromagnetic field exposure in indoor spaces where there are located base stations with distributed antenna system"

The conference that took place on 15-16 July 2021 (Iasi, Romania).

Supply Chain Institute Event

Mrs. Giorgina Mavrouli and Mr. Mihai Stamatiadis of partner OAKINDIS represent VITAL-5G aims, ambitions and use cases in their presentation titled "5G & 4.0 in Logistics".

The above was presented at Supply Chain Institute "Case Studies Generating New Knowledge" event on 10/05/2021 (Case studies now favouring originally in Greek language).

VITAL-5G Deliverables Submitted

Deliverable	Lead Institution	Observation Level	Submission Date
Q1-2 VITAL-5G System Specifications and Architecture	ONL	Public	November 2021
Q1-4 Testing and Validation Methodology	eBOS	Public	December 2021
Q2-1 NetApps (Bespoke and Open Repository Design)	WEEC	Public	December 2021
Q2-2 VITAL-5G experimentation platform - Early Staging Area	NOW	Public	March 2022
Q2-3 Research on VITAL-5G infrastructure requirements & Extensions	ORIG	Public	March 2022
Q1-1 VITAL-5G Market Analysis report	BEIA	Confidential	September 2022
Q1-4 Data Management Plan	INLE	Public	December 2021
Q1-1 Final Annual report on project progress	WINGS	Confidential	January 2022

Publications

- Andreas Karabalis, Nikolaos Kiglatonas, Vasilios Catakis, Alexandros Voulas, George Sotiri, Maria Terdaki, Just Brunn, Gadi Land, Konstantinos Tzafas, VITAL-5G: A novel 5G enabled partner for vertical innovations in Transport and Logistics, Transportation Research Proceedings (2021)
- Nico Biondi, Giorgina Mavrouli, Gadi Land, Juan Benitez, Alexander Vukobratovic, Vasilios Catakis, Konstantinos Tzafas, Kostas Katsaros, Ioannis Katsaros, Adina Rosca, Juhani M. Harjaneva, Network Applications (NetApps) as a 5G Enabler for Transport & Logistics (T&L) Services: The VITAL-5G Approach, 2022 IEEE 8th 5G Summit, 2-10 June 2022
- Andreas Biondi, Christos Patasikas-Sakellarios, Maria Terdaki, Ioan Constantin Andrei, Barthelemy, Cyprian B. Coma, Constantin F. Caruntu, Automated Onboarding, Testing and Validation Framework for NetApps, 2021 International Symposium on Signals, Circuits and Systems (ISSCS), 15-16 July 2021
- Maria Terdaki, Vasilios Catakis, Todor Petroski, Evaluation of electromagnetic field exposure in indoor spaces where there are 5G enabled base stations with distributed antenna systems, 2021 International Symposium on Signals, Circuits and Systems (ISSCS), 15-16 July 2021
- Maria Terdaki, Todor Petroski, Vasilios Catakis, Evaluation of electromagnetic field exposure in the vicinity of mobile phone base stations, IEEE International Black Sea Conference on Communications and Networking, 24-28 May 2021

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Project Objectives

- 1 Foster the development and sharing of novel vertical-specific and vertical-agnostic NetApps for the T&L sector
- 2 Deliver a testing and validation experimentation facility that will allow T&L stakeholders to deploy and benchmark the performance of their NetApps
- 3 Showcase the added value of 5G connectivity for multi-modal logistics services across European roads, seas and rivers
- 4 Provide customized and virtualized access to network and T&L infrastructure resources, enabling service provisioning to 3rd parties
- 5 Enable novel business models development for open, integrated and cooperative services across multiple domains
- 6 Foster the development and advancement of a T&L centred ecosystem by bringing together key vertical stakeholders with SMEs

VITAL-5G Annual Review

The annual online meeting of the VITAL-5G Project was held on the 7th and 8th of October 2021, that took place virtually. The project progress received positive feedback by the European Commission. Recommendations were given to maximize the project's impact which the project will follow throughout its implementation moving forward.

What's Next for VITAL-5G?

As the project matures and with COVID-19 restrictions easing, physical participation events and meetings will be one of the consortium's priorities.

One of the largest scientific conferences of the field, the 2022 IEEE 8th 5G Summit will be attended by representatives of the project, announcing the next newsletter for:

- We are committed to organize and attend activities designed for various stakeholders and maximize the impact of VITAL-5G.
- 3rd party experimenters will be able to apply for access to our resources and given the chance to develop their own T&L NetApps.

What to expect going forward

- 1 Organization of more common workshops with other ICT-4I projects
- 2 Active participation in SCPPP working groups and production of publications including journal papers and white papers
- 3 Release of a demo presenting the VITAL-5G platform and the development and onboarding of NetApps
- 4 The full release of the VITAL-5G platform and calls for 3rd party experimenters to make use of its resources
- 5 The setup of the project's first hackathon for both academic and industrial users and the possibility to collaborate directly with the VITAL-5G consortium
- 6 Increased participation to conferences and webinars to present our results that will transform the T&L sector

Stay updated on VITAL-5G's developments and events

Figure 6: The 2nd Newsletter of VITAL-5G.

2.2 Evaluation, Statistics and Impact Status

2.2.1 Website Statistics

Since the beginning of the project, our website has been visited by **more than 1200 unique visitors** as shown in Figure 7, which has been met with the respective KPI as set in the VITAL-5G GA. We are on track of reaching the KPI set to be met by the end of the project of **over 2000 unique visitors**. This will be achieved by releasing more newsletters, press releases, organising more online trainings and events which we will require users to register and replay them through our website as well as advertising the website in every given opportunity on our social media.

Figure 7: Unique visitors on VITAL-5G's website as extracted through Google analytics

2.2.2 Social Media Statistics

Concerning **Twitter**, as shown in Figure 8, our account has **275 followers** at the time this deliverable is being composed, **already exceeding the KPI set by the GA (200 followers)**. In **LinkedIn**, as shown in Figure 9, our followers have been acquired organically. We have not yet met with the KPI set of 200 but the numbers are really in our favour as by the end of the project we project to surpass that number by a big difference. This will be done by promoting our LinkedIn page in all future outreach activities and content produced as well as by constantly posting updates of the project, its results and engaging with all stakeholders.

Figure 8: Twitter metrics as of the 8th of June 2022.

Figure 9: LinkedIn followers as of the 8th of June 2022.

2.2.3 Evaluation of Outreach Activities

The project is now at M18 and while some of the KPIs agreed on the GA have been either met or are on a good path to be met, some are in need of swift actions which are planned to be taken. The metrics that will be used each step of the way to measure the success of our outreach activities are presented in Table 3.

The consortium members have been actively participating in industrial exhibitions, presenting the project, its results and future actions. The KPI set for at least 10 such participations will be met in the future with the project being already half-way to meeting that goal.

Concerning the **scientific publications**, although the project has faced some issues with the lack of journal publications in 5G technology relevant journals, we are alert of the situation and in the following months, as the project will produce more results and 3rd party experimenters will be using our platform, we are confident that we will be exceeding the 10 publications necessary. Our participation in scientific conferences is strong and we are well on our way to meet the defined KPI. An example of our presence in such conferences is the project's participation at the 2022 EuCNC & 6G Summit with the paper entitled "*Network Applications (NetApps) as a 5G booster for T&L Services: The VITAL-5G approach*" as described in Section 2.1.1. Participation in such a prestigious and impactful event in the area of telecommunications is a very big step in proving that our project's concept and future results are of interest to the stakeholder groups of interest to the project. The project is also set to present its work in the upcoming TRA 2022 Conference and other conferences and expos to solidify its position in the telecommunication and T&L ecosystem thus enabling us to attract more external experimenters for onboarding them on the project's platform.

Concerning our participation in the **5G-PPP Working Groups**, VITAL-5G has representatives into **5 Work Groups**⁸ (Vision and Societal Challenges, SME, 5G for CAM, Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation and 5G/Beyond 5G Architecture) as well as to the Technical Board of 5G-PPP. The project envisions participating in more WGs in the next reporting period.

On the **training** front, the first webinar of the project took place on the 5th of April 2022 as described in Section 2.1.2 and a second one followed on the 22nd of June 2022 (the invitation disseminated is shown in Figure 10). The goal of the second webinar was to demonstrate the capabilities of all VITAL-5G's trial sites and testbeds and the opportunities for 3rd party experimenters as a preliminary engagement event to support the objective of the project of onboarding experimenters to the VITAL-5G platform. The VITAL-5G platform was presented with a deep dive in the technical capabilities. This event served as a gateway for the next online workshop entitled "VITAL-5G 3rd Party Engagement Workshop", envisioned to take place on the 7th of July 2022, which will be a prelude of the Hackathon that is set to take place later in the year.

⁸ <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-work-groups/>

Figure 10: Invitation for the 2nd webinar of VITAL-5G that took place on the 22nd of June 2022 disseminated on social media.

The public deliverables of the project are diligently being uploaded in the special section reserved on VITAL-5G's website.

On the **communication** front, the project website and social media are at a very healthy state with both means of online communication reaching and set to exceed the KPIs set.

The project has already published **two newsletters and two press releases**, with more coming up in the next phase of the project. We do not see any problem reaching the KPIs set in that communication metric as with the opening of the platform to 3rd party experimenters and new results coming out, we foresee that heavy dissemination will be required and will be part of our strategy for the upcoming period. The same applies for both the technical and non-technical factsheets of the project.

Videos produced by any VITAL-5G initiative, are uploaded to our YouTube channel and are disseminated through our social media to the targeted communities. We will continue to enrich our video collections and make sure that we reach the video views as promised.

Table 3: Dissemination and communication outcome, metrics and targets.

Communication/ Dissemination Means	Success Indicators	Target Values	Timeline
Project Website	Search Engine Optimization metrics	Online by month 1; Unique visitors from M12: 1000; from M36: 2000	Ready by M1; M1-M36
Social media	#of users/ followers	LinkedIn >200 followers; Twitter > 200 followers; Re-Tweets >200;	M1-M36

Communication/ Dissemination Means	Success Indicators	Target Values	Timeline
		Banners >30	
Press Releases	# of press releases	Press releases: >6	M1-M36; 2 press releases / year
Newsletters	# of publications	Newsletters: >6	M1-M36; 2 Newsletters per year
Video Clips	# of video clips and views	Number of online video clips: >3; Number of video views: > 1000	By M36
Factsheets/ Brochures	# of factsheets and hardcopies	Technical factsheets: 6; Non-technical factsheets: 6; Hardcopies: > 1000	M1-M36
Flyers/ Posters & roll-ups	# of flyers and banners	Project flyers: >3; Posters & roll-up banners: >3	M1-M36
Industrial exhibitions	# of exhibitions	Participation in industrial exhibitions, trade fairs: >10	M7 -M36
Scientific publications	#of publications	Journals/magazines >10; Conferences >30; Conference demonstrations: >6	M7-M36
Workshop Organization & Participation	# of workshops	Workshop (co)organization: 6 Workshop participation: 12	M1-M36
5G PPP programme	Active participation in 5G-PPP Working Groups (WGs)	Number of WGs to contribute: 7 Interactions with initiatives: > 4	M1-M36
Training	# of trainings over the course of the project	Online training tutorials: 3 Number of PhD schools: 2; Webinars: 10	M7-M36
Online Repository	Deliverables accepted by the European Commission	Number of publicly available deliverables: > 19	M1-M36

Stepping on the latest version of D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication activities v1.0, we have created a ranking system to evaluate the progress of each metric as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Dissemination and Outreach KPI grading system.

Grade	Categories	General Actions/Measures
0	Corrective actions necessary	The KPI is far below the expectation in relation to the project's progress. Immediate action is necessary to put it back on track.
1	Needs constant monitoring	The KPI is below the expected value but is on course to reach it. Monitoring is necessary but not further actions.
2	Requires occasional check	The KPI is close to be reached and only occasional check is required.
3	Good progress	The KPI has been or is close to be reached but no actions or additional checks are necessary.
4	Exceeds expectations	The KPI has been met and is over the minimum value set.

Using the proposed system, we have evaluated the metrics set in our previous deliverable (after grouping them by target group), according to the current situation as of the submission of this deliverable. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Dissemination and Outreach KPIs monitoring

Tool/action	Main target group	Type of Metric/Target Value	Value at M18	Grade	Mitigation Actions
Website	End-Users, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Knowledge Providers, General Public	# unique visitors: from M12: 1000; from M36: 2000	1200+	3	No mitigation actions for the moment
Social Media	End-Users, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Knowledge Providers, General Public	LinkedIn >200 followers; Twitter > 200 followers; Re-Tweets >200; Banners >30	LinkedIn: 154 followers Twitter: 227 followers Re-Tweets 60 Banners: 21	4	No mitigation actions for the moment
Videos, online presence on Website and YouTube	End-Users, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Knowledge Providers, General Public	Number of online video clips: >3; Number of video views: > 1000	Number of online video clips: 6 Number of video views: 406	2	The online video clips need to be promoted more in all of our dissemination media to increase viewership.
Press Releases	End-Users, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Knowledge Providers, General Public	Press releases >6	Press releases: (2+1)	3	No mitigation actions for the moment
Publications, participation to conferences	End-Users, Knowledge Providers	Journals/magazines > 10	Journals/magazines: (2) Conferences: 8	2	As more results are produced by the project, the more publications will be produced. We have generated an

Tool/action	Main target group	Type of Metric/Target Value	Value at M18	Grade	Mitigation Actions
		Conferences > 30 Conference demonstrations > 6	Conference demonstrations: 0		internal plan to optimise the output in this metric which will be carefully followed.
Webinars, training events, online distribution on Website, YouTube and Social Media	End-Users, Knowledge Providers	Online training tutorials: 3 Number of PhD schools: 2 Webinars: 10	Online training tutorials: 3 Number of PhD schools: 0 Webinars: 3	2	More trainings will be organised, especially with the upcoming opening of the portal to 3 rd parties. All partners will contribute to the organisation.
Business conferences, industrial expos and networking events	End-Users, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	Participation in industrial exhibitions, trade fair >10	Participation in industrial exhibitions, trade fair: 4	3	No mitigation actions for the moment

3 VITAL-5G Hackathon, Liaison with Innovation Stakeholders and 3rd party Engagement

3.1 Hackathon Organization

The main objective of organizing the hackathon is to understand the needs and requirements of the end users, and to achieve an active interaction with interested 3rd-parties such as SMEs, start-ups, companies, and students from universities and research groups, which all could be engaged as the 3rd party experimenters at a later stage of the VITAL-5G project. The event will be organized in a hybrid manner, with a physical presence on two sites, i.e., Antwerp (Belgium) and Bucharest (Romania), and remote presence from Greece and Italy. All partners involved in WP6 committed to distributing the invitation for participation and gaining more visibility of the activities in this hackathon, as well as to participating in technical sessions.

The hackathon will consist of the three main parts:

- **Technical courses:** The technical sessions that cover topics on i) designing and developing Network Applications for 5G vertical services in T&L sector, ii) on-boarding Network Applications to the NFV infrastructure on all three pilot sites, iii) 5G testbeds as an essential part of each of the pilot sites, and iv) monitoring data from distributed pilot sites. Finally, a hands-on demo will be presented to the participants, showing examples of 5G Network Applications that are already designed and developed in the VITAL-5G projects, which would serve as a starting point for participants to design their own Network Applications, thereby leveraging the data and assets available in the VITAL-5G project.
- **Participants' activities:** This part of the event will include i) the brainstorming session on the Network Application design and development tailored to the 5G vertical services in the T&L sector, ii) the design of the Network Applications and respective interfaces with the VITAL-5G platforms and UEs (e.g., vessel, or AGV), and iii) the presentation of ideas and the Network Application design.
- **Evaluation:** Given the presentations of the designed Network Applications and respective interfaces, the jury will evaluate the ideas and proposals coming from the participants and decide on the hackathon winner.

In order to prepare for the Hackathon, which is envisioned to take place in Spring 2023, the project will organize a pre-hackathon simulation event in the form of an online workshop for 3rd party experimenters in which participants will be asked to prepare a pitch at the end of the workshop which will be graded. This will help the experimenters to better calibrate their pitch for the Hackathon and understand their needs.

3.2 Liaison with Innovation Stakeholders

VITAL-5G project has set as one of its top priorities the engagement of 3rd-parties and for this reason a number of liaisons and initiatives has been launched with several innovation stakeholders such as startup incubators, business accelerators and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH).

3.2.1 Digital Innovation Hubs: Athena Research Centre

eBOS has been in contact with the Athena Research Centre⁹ (ARC) in Greece and liaised in order to establish a fruitful collaboration starting from the participation of ARC's personnel in the pre-hackathon workshop organised in July 2022 as describe in Section 4.4. The mission of ARC is to conduct outstanding research in Informatics and Computational Sciences with substantial social impact, addressing both global challenges and local needs. Athena RC explores a broad spectrum of research areas within the ICT field, as well as topics raised by other scientific fields, industry needs, or societal challenges, making it a valuable stakeholder that would engage with VITAL-5G assets and become a 3rd party experimenter.

⁹ <https://www.athenarc.gr/en>

Further to research, innovation is also a fundamental pillar of Athena RC's mission. Its several Research Institutes, Units, Spin-off companies and particularly its dedicated innovation-support Unit (Corallia) create a fertile technological innovation ecosystem and intensify systematic efforts to bring to market research and technological results, which also intersects with the goals set by VITAL-5G and through the exchange of best practices, the exploitation strategy of the project can be refined.

3.2.2 Digital Innovation Hubs: Digital Innovation HUBs and Collaborative Platform for Cyber-Physical Systems (HUBCAP)

HUBCAP¹⁰ is a one-stop-shop for European SMEs wanting to join the Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) revolution. It builds on eight established Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in seven European countries, each deeply embedded in its regional digital innovation ecosystem, and offering specialist expertise, experimental capabilities, and focused application domain knowledge in CPS Engineering. From this base, HUBCAP is set to create a growing and sustainable pan-European network that will offer SMEs opportunities to undertake experiments, seek investment, and access expertise and training. This will be enabled by a cloud-based open collaboration platform with a 'sandbox' capability to help potential users trial new CPS design technology before investment.

The HUBCAP Collaboration Platform is composed of two main subsystems:

- A Collaboration Portal (HCP) conceived to foster collaboration among SMEs and DIHs,
- A Sandboxing Middleware (HSM) designed to offer a simple and dynamic solution to access the developed solutions.

The sandbox is represented by a set of virtual machines that communicate by using an isolated network and interact with each other. The data sharing in this configuration is achieved by using a shared storage, the Sandbox Shared Storage.

An illustration of the HUBCAP platform is given in Figure 10.

Figure 11: The Sandbox Environment button available in the Collaboration Portal home page.

¹⁰ <https://www.hubcap.eu/>

BEIA is involved in the HUBCAP project leading tasks related to System Integration and Handling Intellectual Property Rights of Services. The expertise gained in the HUBCAP platform, especially the ‘sandbox’ concept, can be used to offer ‘safe’ experimentation opportunities for 3rd party experimenters within VITAL-5G.

3.2.3 Digital Innovation Hubs: Trans4MERS

The European Advanced Manufacturing Support Centre (ADMA) Trans4MERS¹¹ will accelerate factories to become Factories of the Future embracing the ecological, digital, and societal challenges. The project is best positioned to support ambitious SMEs on their transformation journey, designed to ensure that Europe embraces the transformation of the economy and society and brings its benefits to All citizens and businesses. ADMA Trans4MERS will build and deliver assistance with digital competencies (underpinned by technology: high-performance computing, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity) and training in advanced skills in digital technologies in SMEs, contributing to Europe’s strategic autonomy, and accelerating deployment and best use in areas of public interest and the private sector.

The project will operationalize the Smart Specialisation Strategy priority areas of Manufacturing (Industry4.0 and Industry 5.0) in 25 of the EU-27 and where industry overlaps with ICT, energy, health, and Key Digital Technologies considering the ethical, data, security, and equality challenges.

Figure 12: The structure of the ADMA layers

The overall objective of **ADMA Trans4MERS** is to realize an-European assistance and training for SMEs. This will be operationalized through the realization of a digital platform, reinforcement of the **DIHs, EENs, and VETs** by enabling **xChange** with Trans4MERS in all member states to guide SMEs on their transformation journey. The providers and users will gain priority access to a repository of services/tools for assistance and training, a user-friendly dashboard to add gamification among the learning network, complemented by a Trans4MERS application to enhance and capture the experience for impactful services/tools.

VITAL-5G partner BEIA is involved in this project and will cross-over best practices from the project, especially the assistance and training for SME users which could benefit VITAL-5G when engaging with 3rd party Network Application developers.

3.2.4 EIT Digital

EIT Digital¹² is at the forefront of innovation by mobilizing a pan-European multi-stakeholder open-innovation ecosystem comprised by top European corporations, SMEs, start-ups, universities and research institutes, where

¹¹ <https://trans4mers.eu/>

¹² <https://www.eitdigital.eu/>

students, academics, professionals as well as business developers and investors have the opportunity to address the technology, talent, skills, business and capital needs of digital entrepreneurship.

EIT Digital answers specific innovation needs by, for example, finding the right partners to bring technology to the market, supporting the scale-up of digital technology ventures, attracting talent and developing their digital knowledge and skills.

As the project evolves and produces results, we can use EIT Digital's expertise in developing digital products and services to incorporate it in our business plan and maximise the exploitation potential of the project's results. Additionally, through the pool of available digital entrepreneurial talent that EIT Digital has access to, we aim to leverage it in order to enhance the utilization of the VITAL-5G platform and attract high-quality 3rd party experimenters which will have the two-fold role of: 1) the development of novel products and services, and, 2) enhancing the VITAL-5G ecosystem where collaborations can be formed and lead to the long-term sustainability of the project.

3.2.5 Orange Romania 5G-Startup Lab

Orange Romania opened an Orange 5G Lab¹³ dedicated to the 5G technology, in partnership with the "CAMPUS" Research Institute, part of the Politechnica University of Bucharest. The Orange 5G Lab in Bucharest is part of a network of 9 Orange 5G Lab announced by the Orange group.

The Orange 5G Lab initiative meets this demand for companies to experiment, developed and aims to help economic players and researchers to better understand the opportunities, value and utility of 5G. VITAL-5G aims to incorporate the Orange 5G Lab to its core ecosystem and extend invitations to the future 3rd party engagement activities.

Entrepreneurs and developers will be able to test their existing solutions and services, as well as try out new use cases, thus contributing to the co-innovation ecosystem that will support the transformation of future business models and processes. Interested researchers will also find a place to innovate, taking existing 5G findings to new horizons. The new space represents one more initiative marking the common effort between Orange Romania and UPB to support new business projects, as well as research and innovation initiatives.

¹³ <https://5glab.orange.ro/>

4 3rd party engagement activities

The 3rd party engagement activities are the main focus of task T6.3, and they are currently ongoing with the objective to engage and interact with the 3rd party experimenters well in advance, even before all three VITAL-5G pilot sites become available for the experimentation activities.

4.1 Introduction

The 3rd party engagement activities are considered as pre-experimentation, and they have been executed in two phases:

- Collecting input on the available assets from all three pilot sites, and advertising material on the project website, and,
- Organizing dissemination activities such as webinars and hackathon to advertise the pilot sites and the collected input on the available assets.

The main purpose of these pre-experimentation activities is to show the exact capabilities of 5G pilot sites and different Network Applications to the potential 3rd party experimenters, thereby gaining more visibility from the external participants. These activities are shown as engagement activities in Figure 12, stretching over 2022 until September, when the first on-boarding activities are planned.

Figure 13: Timeline of engagement activities with the 3rd party experimenters.

The first phase is to collect the input from all partners involved in the pilot sites, and made a clear overview of all assets in the three pilot sites that are either already available or will become available for the 3rd party experimenters in the upcoming months, and remain available until the end of the VITAL-5G project.

The overall input consists of Network Applications, Data, 5G testbed components, and Results, which will be made available to the 3rd party experimenters during the span of the VITAL-5G project. In Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15, we show the overview of these assets for all three pilot sites, i.e., Antwerp, Galati, and Athens, respectively.

Planned engagement activities such as outreach activities in the form of webinars, and interactive sessions and activities in the form of workshops and hackathons will enable us to get in touch with the potential 3rd party experimenters and start engaging them into VITAL-5G activities in all three pilot sites. To add more details about the process for engaging with 3rd party experimenters and how they can apply for access to the VITAL-5G platform a special section on the VITAL-5G website will be created. The process is further described in Section 4.2.

4.2 Target audiences & available assets

In the VITAL-5G website, there is a dedicated section which serves as an advertisement to potentially interested 3rd parties¹⁴ that wish to know more about the available assets to the test sites with analytical information in order for them to tailor their experiments and thus have a better match with the upcoming call for experiments. An overview of the assets can be seen in Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15, for all three pilot sites, i.e., Antwerp, Galati, and Athens, respectively.

Figure 14: Available assets per asset category: Antwerp trial site.

Figure 15: Available assets per asset category: Galati trial site.

¹⁴ <https://www.vital5g.eu/3rd-party-experimenters-participation/>

Figure 16: Available assets per asset category: Athens trial site.

In addition to the overview, interested parties can also see the availability of the assets (earliest possible access date), a detailed description of the assets as well as the type of each asset. In order for experimenters to choose the correct website, there is also an additional section on what they can leverage from each respective site. A brief description of all assets is provided respectively in Table 6, Table 7 and Table 8. Each site has specialized assets for each use case it tackles in the project. For each site, we present its respective use case. More information can be found in D1.1 – “Report on Use Case Requirements – v1.0” and D1.2 – “System Specifications and Architecture”.

Use case 1 (UC1): Automated Vessel Transport (Port of Antwerp)

This use case deals with the application of 5G technology in a smart port context. It will be performed using a vessel provided by Seafar at the Port of Antwerp (PoA). The main goal is to showcase the automation of vessel-based logistics transport leveraging the modern 5G communications technology. This vessel will be running in a normal operational schedule, but for this use case, it will also be outfitted with additional 5G connectivity which will support high-bandwidth (preferably full HD) camera feeds, real-time sensor data coming from the vessels to the command centre, and real-time steering commands to the remote vessel.

We aim to build up a real-time digital twin around the vessel to support the remotely controlled (and later on autonomous) vessels. In parallel, real-time route planning will be foreseen to optimize the port operations and to avoid idle times, based on berthing time slots provided by the port authorities and terminal operators, while the optimization will be performed based on Machine Learning/ Artificial Intelligence (ML/AI) methodologies. The applications developed in this use case, make use of the following types of data: vessels’ location, schedule, perception data including camera streams, Light Detection And Ranging (LiDAR) point cloud, and slot data to calculate the optimal navigation speed that needs to be held by vessels to meet their slot at terminals/locks etc.

Table 6: Overview of assets and their availability with reference to Figure 13.

Asset	Type of asset	Availability (from)	Description
On-board data collection and interfacing for vessels (VS8)	Network Application	September 2022	Network Application responsible for collecting public vessel data on speed, location and heading, and for providing other Network Applications with a real-time influx of the collected data.
Remote vessel monitoring (VS5)	Network Application	2023	Network Application in charge of assisting the captain on-board or at the shore control centre while navigating through the monitoring dashboard, which contains a camera feed, a map with the vessel location, the actual vessel speed, the advised vessel speed and a map with the nearby objects.
Remote digital twin (VA5)	Network Application	2023	Network Application responsible for creating a real-time digital twin that constructs a local copy of a situational awareness model. It makes use of all available sensor data to build a real-time model of the environment.
Navigation Speed Optimizer (VS7)	Network Application	September 2022	Network Application in charge of helping vessel operators (human or computer-based) in their daily navigation tasks by providing them with an optimal navigation speed so that they arrive in time, resulting in reduced waiting times and fuel consumption.
Real-time data from vessels: location, speed, heading	Data	September 2022	Open datasets with historical data on the location/speed/heading of the vessel to be available on Zenodo.
Real-time calculated optimal navigation speed	Data	September 2022	Open datasets with real-time calculated optimal navigation speed as an output of Network Application VS7 to be available on Zenodo. Optimal speed calculated based on the open data on the location/speed/heading of the vessels.
Pre-configured 5G slices	5G testbed	2023	5G slices provisioned during the 3 rd party experimenters' trials. Different network slices (eMBB and uRLLC) to be provisioned in a pre-configured manner.
New 5G slices to be provisioned	5G testbed	2023	5G slices provisioned during the 3 rd party experimenters' trials. Different network slices (eMBB and uRLCC) to be provisioned in a dynamic manner.
Network/platform KPIs from monitoring platform on 5G testbed	Results	2023	Measurement logs from executed experiments provided through the Vital-5G monitoring platform.
*once defined, a more detailed overview of availability will be updated on the project website, in particular for the activities planned for 2023 (month to be further specified)			

Use case 2 (UC2): 5G Connectivity and Data-Enabled Assisted Navigation Using IoT Sensing and Video Cameras (Galati River port)

Unlike UC1, which focuses on creating a Digital Twin to support remotely controlled ships in a sea port, Use Case 2 focuses on the implementation of a data-enabled assisted navigation application using an Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensing system and video cameras installed in a river port (Galati) and on ships and barges (cargos). The Galati port is an entry point for large shipping traffic from the Black Sea towards continental Europe and is part of the Rhine-Danube Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) Corridor2. It is the largest port on the Danube River and the second largest Romanian port. Therefore, there are a host of different functional challenges associated with navigation in a river port as opposed to a sea port, as it is outlined below.

The UC application proposed will permit a safer river port operation and more security regarding navigation of ships with the help of assisted operation / navigation even in severe weather and water conditions.

The Romanian test case study will be performed on a series of ships belonging to CNFR NAVROM. NAVROM is a Romanian river transport company, carrying millions of tons of various goods through both internal (Galati, Constanta etc.) and external routes to Ukraine, Bulgaria, Austria, Germany etc. It has a tradition of over 100 years, being an important European inland shipowner.

In the activity of operating the ships, it is necessary to implement technologies for communication and monitoring of voyages, as a source for correcting the weak points. Thus, to avoid stationary downtime due to navigation errors, and to respectively reduce as much as possible the transport of empty units, while achieving a higher percentage of loading, better communication between ships and dispatchers as well as between ships and ports of operation is required. This can be achieved by a real-time connectivity of the radio and video navigation equipment of the sensors that monitor the operating parameters of the ship with the dispatcher office and / or the safety of the navigation department. Also, for better sailing safety, a connection between the decision departments (the Fleet operation department) and ships is necessary for getting out of difficult situations.

All sensors and cameras will enable the interoperable wireless protocols over a private 5G network and will permit the extension of Internet connectivity of the sensing system. Several sensors, that will be described in this section, such as global positioning system (GPS), humidity, smoke, engine power sensors located in the machine room, will be installed on the ship and barges. These sensors provide relevant information such as velocity, heading, water and wind speed, etc. to the ship local monitoring equipment, allowing the captain and crew to take proper decisions and supporting on-board diagnosis. The crew will also have access to live video streaming from the surroundings through high-definition video cameras in order to achieve high-resolution video streams, high connectivity and low latency that is uniquely offered by 5G.

The Galati port 5G testbed will be based on the existing Orange 5G facility built with components from ICT-17's 5G-EVE project; it will be upgraded with additional 3GPP Rel.16 features and extended to provide coverage at the Galati port.

Table 7: Overview of assets and their availability with reference to Figure 14.

Asset	Type of asset	Availability (from)	Description
Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & post-processing (VA2)	Network Application	September 2022	In charge of data ingestion, fusion and post-processing functionality from distributed data sources.

Asset	Type of asset	Availability (from)	Description
Predictive maintenance (VA3)	Network Application	2023	Responsible for modelling various machine learning techniques to achieve functions like automated labelling, outlier detection, trace back analysis, graphical representations, predictions/forecasts for the near-future and therefore offer advanced diagnostics to aid decision making and specifically for the case of predictive maintenance. The results of these techniques may be used for monitoring purposes as well as by other applications.
Positions of ships and obstacles	Data	September 2022	Open datasets with historical data on the positions of ships and obstacles to be available on Zenodo.
Sensor data (weather and air quality)	Data	September 2022	Open datasets with historical records on the sensor data (weather and air quality) to be available on Zenodo.
Pre-configured 5G slices	5G testbed	2023	5G slices provisioned during the 3 rd party experimenters' trials. Different network slices (eMBB and uRLLC) to be provisioned in a pre-configured manner.
New 5G slices to be provisioned	5G testbed	2023	5G slices provisioned during the 3 rd party experimenters' trials. Different network slices (eMBB and uRLLC) are envisioned to be provisioned in a dynamic manner.
Network KPIs from monitoring platform on 5G testbed	Results	2023	Measurement logs on network KPIs from executed experiments provided through the Vital-5G monitoring platform.
Risk analysis data, alarms, relevant analytics info	Results	2023	Logs on risk analysis, alarms, and other relevant analytics information from executed experiments provided through the Vital-5G monitoring platform.
*once defined, a more detailed overview of availability will be updated on the project website, in particular for the activities planned for 2023 (month to be further specified)			

Use case 3: Automation and Remote Operation of Freight Logistics (Athens)

Diakinisis S.A. is a 3rd party Logistics (3PL) provider with many depots across Greece. The depot that will be used in the framework of the VITAL-5G project incorporates all daily operations met in a typical warehouse, namely, receiving, put-away to stock, picking (and replenishment of picking from stock locations), checking - final preparation of orders (packaging and labelling), and shipping as well as value-adding services such as co-packing.

This use case intends to demonstrate the feasibility of applying the 5G technology in an overall Logistics context, for optimizing warehousing operations through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) as used by Network Application VS1. This system will make use of the 5G-EVE Athens testbed which will be upgraded to stand-alone and extended at the warehouse premises. The operation of AGVs can be automated and remotely assisted using HD video streaming functionality to enable human interaction (Network Application VS2), while additional AI/ML techniques will be introduced for post-processing operational data in order to improve the end-to-end functionality of the warehouse ecosystem (Network Application VA1). Figure 45 depicts the overall concept of the Athens UC.

Table 8: Overview of assets and their availability with reference to Figure 15.

Asset	Type of asset	Availability (from)	Description
Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & automation (VA1)	Network Application	2023	Responsible for the data ingestion and two-way communication with on-site equipment, decision support using rules and inference, monitoring and field assistance.
Digital Twin & simulated warehouse environment which includes virtual Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs)	Facility	2023	Experiment execution using the digital twin and simulated warehouse environment with virtual AGVs.
Partial access to AGVs	Facility	2023	Agreed and coordinated access to the AGVs (indoor robotic platform) in the Athens trial facility will be possible.
Data from mounted sensors in the warehouse	Data	2023	The Environmental Sensors pack provides data from sensors (temperature, humidity, vibration, luminosity) deployed on various locations in the warehouse environment. The data will be available in the form of open datasets.
Non-sensitive historical data from warehouse and AGV operations	Data	2023	Open datasets with non-sensitive historical data from warehouse and AGV operations to be available on Zenodo.
Pre-configured 5G slices	5G testbed	2023	5G slices provisioned during the 3 rd party experimenters' trials. Different network slices (eMBB and uRLLC) to be provisioned in a pre-configured manner.
New 5G slices to be provisioned	5G testbed	2023	5G slices provisioned during the 3 rd party experimenters' trials. Different network slices (eMBB and uRLLC) to be provisioned with the ability of the user to select the slice in a static manner..
Network KPIs from monitoring platform on 5G testbed	Results	2023	Measurement logs on network KPIs from executed experiments provided through the Vital-5G monitoring platform.
*once defined, a more detailed overview of availability will be updated on the project website, in particular for the activities planned for 2023 (month to be further specified)			

4.3 Instructions to experimenters

A section of the VITAL-5G website will be dedicated to attracting and aiding 3rd party experimenters in accessing the resources offered. In order to build rapport with the stakeholders that want to engage with us, we must first identify their needs. For this, we have created and launched an expression of interest form that will be disseminated through every available channel as shown in Figure 16.

We consider the feedback from the potential experimenters very important for understanding the needs of the community. This will serve as a two-way communication and resource building tool between the project partners and the 3rd party experimenters. The platform for accessing resources, will be dynamically evolving as more users utilise our resources.

We envision the portal to be a resource to 3rd parties in multiple ways. Except from access to resources and monitoring the availability, the portal would include access to educational resources, past webinars, links to publications as well as a guide on how-to for the portal and setting up the testing environment. The portal will also include a calendar where the experimenters will be able to book one-on-one sessions with the personnel from the pilot sites for support.

After the feedback has been collected and the number of interested parties has been specified, we will then launch the matchmaking section of the website, where 3rd party experimenters, will be able to choose which pilot site want to access, what type of experiment they want to launch (e.g., Network Application development and testing, experimentation with 5G slices, etc.) and any other service they would like to access in the pilot sites. The platform will also serve as an exploitation tool for the project's results.

Expression of interest for 3rd Party Experimenters in Transport & Logistics 5G applications in the context of the VITAL-5G project

Your data will be taken care of in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

* Required

Name *

Your answer

Surname *

Your answer

E-mail *

Your answer

Job Title *

Your answer

Organisation Type *

Start-up
 SME
 Company
 Research Institute
 Other:

Experimentation and resource needs for accessing the testbeds of VITAL-5G *
 (e.g., 5G testbed facilities, VITAL-5G NetApps, NetApp blueprints, or data collected from pilot sites). Please describe your interests in performing experimentation and using resources from the pilot sites in the VITAL-5G. (<https://www.vital5g.eu/3rd-party-experimenters-participation/>)

Your answer

Submit
Clear form

Never submit passwords through Google Forms.

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Google Forms

Figure 17: Expression of interest form for 3rd party experimenters.

4.4 Target audiences to attract 3rd party experimenters

Our dissemination strategy is tailored to attract a large number of stakeholders in the T&L sectors who are interested in accessing resources for experimentation and to improve their services. The aim is to attract large industries, SMEs, start-ups, research institutes as well as motivated individuals including graduate students.

We are interested in attracting a large number of people, with the goal of creating a VITAL-5G ecosystem that will be comprised by players from all target audiences and that will bring together policymakers, general audiences, scientists, industry experts that will give constant feedback and improving the project services.

It is thus of extreme importance that activities are organised that target all these different groups. There is need for both joint events with other projects as well as key representatives from our target groups.

To that end, we will organise in July 2022, a workshop that will serve both as an introductory course to the use of 5G in T&L sectors as well as a first glimpse into the provision of assets to 3rd party experimenters in order to attract interest. Following the workshop, we will gather data from the participants that will aid in both improving the platform as well as retaining an initial core of engaged individuals which will help us grow interest overtime.

A Hackathon will also be organised as described in Section 3.1., after Spring 2023 that will be a massive outreach event to the interested communities that will drive people to the use of the platform and exploitation of the project's resources.

4.5 Maximising impact

Making resources available to 3rd party experimenters is multi-beneficial to the project. Not only is it part of its core commitments as described in the project's GA, but it is also a driving force to promote and better the services provided by the project.

By making resources available to 3rd party experimenters the project aims to:

- i) Provide value to the various T&L communities and associated entities by creating a synergistic environment where test sites can interact with stakeholders and co-develop products. These products will reinforce the VITAL-5G business model and drive innovation in the T&L sector.
- ii) Create better services through stakeholders' input on the performance of the platform and their evaluation output
- iii) Identifying flaws that may be overlooked when developing the platform and through a feedback cycle, continuously improving and attracting more people to use our assets
- iv) Building on WP5 – Commercialization and Innovation, new collaborations can be forged through the interaction between experimenters and site personnel leading to new products and patents.

Most importantly, through the engagement activities of the project, we want to build our own VITAL-5G community and continuously grow it by attracting more experimenters and expanding our network which will be vital to the sustainability of what was built after the project's end date.

Education programs for transport and logistics are expected to exhibit methods for ensuring that students will learn as many of the Universal Concepts at the undergraduate level. In a Master's level course, there will be greater specialisation and it would not be possible to cover as many of these areas. The Chartered Institute of Logistics and Transport (CILT) supports the T&L professionals. They are the leading international voice for supply chain, logistics and transport.

The Key Knowledge Areas were developed and endorsed by the International Council of CILT¹⁵ in 2002. The Key Knowledge Areas (KKA) provide the basis for the educational requirements for Chartered Membership. They describe the subjects, disciplines and tools studied and practised by their members. They also provide the framework for the design, delivery, and examination of CILT education programs and CILT accreditation of external programs including university degrees.

¹⁵ <https://ciltinternational.org/>

5 VITAL-5G External Advisory Board

5.1 Recruitment Process

The External Advisory Board (EAB) was convened under the responsibility of the Project Coordinator (WINGS) at the end of January 2022. The project faced some delays in forming its EAB mainly due to long waiting periods for hearing from candidates and the denial of a few of promising names causing the process to start all over again (identification of new candidates, sending invitations and waiting for response). The EAB is now finalized and during its first meeting, the project progress and plans were presented to its members in order to receive feedback and re-align our goals according to current market and academic trends.

Table 9: Composition of VITAL-5G's External Advisory Board.

VITAL-5G External Advisory Board Members (EAB) member	Organization	Background / Expertise	Country	VITAL-5G partner liaison
Yanying Li	ALICE	Transport & Logistics alliance	International	EBOS
Pablo Segura			International	EBOS
Dinos Katsaros	ICCS	EU projects / 5G-IANA Coordinator	International	WINGS
Boris Wenzel (President)	TIC4.0	T&L Standards Organization	International	WINGS
Norbert Klettner (Vice-President)			International	WINGS
Chiara Iorfida	Cosco shipping Lines Spain	Port logistics, shipping, multimodal transports	ES	WINGS
Pedro Perez			ES	WINGS
Chris Andreikos	Found.ation / Pixelocracy	SW/Platform development, 3rd party engagement	EL	EBOS

5.2 Advisory Board Mission and Skills

The External Advisory Board (EAB) of VITAL-5G and its population with key stakeholders of varying expertise which stand to significantly assist the project in reaching its goals and ensure that the project outcomes have real-world applications and can create significant impact in the T&L sector as well as in Network Application based, 5G-enabled services.

Moreover, a careful selection of candidates was taking place within the project, as it was important to not have overlapping expertise in the EAB but rather construct it in such a way that diverse backgrounds would be represented from the private sector, research, and academia to large T&L stakeholders, SMEs and SW developers.

Such a composition guarantees that the project will receive well-rounded feedback from the EAB covering all relevant sections of the project's work. The composition of the VITAL-5G EAB is shown in Table 9, while its first meeting took place in March 2022, where the project's work during the first year was presented to them, along with the future plans.

5.3 First Advisory Board Meeting

The first Advisory Board meeting took place on the 14th of March 2022. In the meeting, the project's goals and objectives were presented as well as the progress achieved during Year 1. After presenting the current status, the future steps for Year 2 and beyond as well as the timeline envisioned were brought forward.

Following these presentations, the Advisory Board members gave their feedback on the work performed so far as well as helping the VITAL-5G partners re-focus the next steps that need to be taken as well as assessing the potential impact of the project's work. Finally, a recommendation was given to improve the final outcome and impact of the project. Figure 17 is a screenshot of the meeting's agenda.

Monday 14 th March 2022		
10:00 – 10.10 (CET)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Introduction round ○ Agenda acceptance 	Kostas Trichias (WINGS) ALL
10:10 – 10.25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Project Overview <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is the project about ○ Scope and key objectives 	Kostas Trichias (WINGS)
10:25 – 10.45	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Technical Management Overview <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is the project building (NetApps, Experimentation platform, 5G-testbeds)? ○ How does it all come together? 	Giada Landi (NXW)
10:45 – 11.05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Market & Business aspects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Targeted stakeholders ○ T&L market analysis ○ Relevant business models 	Ronan Frizzell (ICP), Kostas Trichias (WINGS),
11:05 – 11.25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Antwerp Trial site presentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ T&L and 5G-testbed facilities ○ Targeted Use Cases, T&L services and NetApps ○ Current status, achieved progress & trial plans ○ Next steps for Year 2 	Ali Anwar, Nina Slamnik (IMEC)
Coffee break (11.25 – 11.30)		
11:30 – 11.50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Athens Trial site presentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ T&L and 5G-testbed facilities ○ Targeted Use Cases, T&L services and NetApps ○ Current status, achieved progress & trial plans ○ Next steps for Year 2 	Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Christina Lessi (OTE),
11:50 – 12.10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Galati (Danube) Trial site presentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ T&L and 5G-testbed facilities ○ Targeted Use Cases, T&L services and NetApps ○ Current status, achieved progress & trial plans ○ Next steps for Year 2 	George Suci (BEIA), Marius Iordache (ORO)
12:10 – 12.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dissemination, communication & outreach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D&C plan & targets ○ Achieved progress and current status ○ 3rd party participation/experimentation plan ○ Next steps for Year 2 	Andreas Kartakoulis (EBOS), Nina Slamnik (IMEC)
12:30 – 13.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ AdvB members feedback <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Free discussion & feedback ○ The good and the bad ○ Potential improvement points ○ How to maximize impact 	ALL
End of Advisory Board meeting (13.00 CET)		

Figure 18: Agenda for the Advisory Board meeting that took place on the 12th of March 2022.

The first topic discussed in the meeting was regarding the feedback from the Advisory board. Yanying Li asked when to expect the feedback and proposed to explicitly mention during the presentation where the board's advice is needed. Giada Landi emphasized the importance of the Advisory board's input on the concept of Network Applications and whether the direction is reasonable or if some other perspective should be considered.

Dinos Katsaros expressed that the stakeholder ecosystem in the project should be more evidently sketched, particularly the role of Network Applications and what they bring on top of the existing VNF packages. He found slide 12 to be an essential piece of information that should be done for the other assets as well, explaining how to make use of them and the benefits for external users, such as 3rd party experimenters.

Yanying Li suggested that it would be fantastic to achieve TRL8 during the project duration already and proposed to engage potential users during the development to ensure that the final TRL8 applications are something end-users need.

Dinos Katsaros asked about the plan for AI data feeding, specifically for diagnostics elements and orchestration elements. Marius explained that utilization and throughput data can be offered to the module, and there is no issue with sharing this type of data from the platform. He also highlighted the different levels where AI takes place, including AI mechanisms at the Network Application level, AI-driven tools implemented within the platform itself, and intent-based management.

Dinos Katsaros asked why Autonomous navigation is running on the infrastructure and not on the vessel directly, as is the case for the automotive approach. The answer was that it is cost-efficient to offload the computation to the infrastructure, and the latency requirements are not so stringent compared to vehicles on highways. Another factor is that the reaction time is larger given that the speed of the vessel is quite different from the speed of the cars on the highways. He also suggested clarifying the name "Autonomous navigation" as it refers to complete autonomous navigation of a vessel, even though there is always a captain on-board.

Regarding the whole procedure of service provisioning, Dinos Katsaros asked if it includes setting up a network slice or if it is decoupled. Marius explained that there is a manual way of configuring network slices at the moment, and users will be assigned to different network slices based on their requirements. Giada Landi clarified that the capabilities offered by different platforms are very heterogeneous, and at the platform level, they decided to proceed with a flexible approach. They will automate the slice configuration where possible, but in other cases, the configuration will be mapping of the Network Applications to the already defined network slices. The issue is more related to the operations than the technical design, and B2B relationships between entities (operations, developers) are needed in that case, and SLA has to be established.

Dinos Katsaros provided some final comments, suggesting that the relation between the business ecosystem and the technical platform can be improved, providing more clarity to all participants, including the 3rd party experimenters. He also suggested highlighting the challenges of orchestrating Network Applications, including domain-specific challenges, such as orchestration on top of the OBUs that are on the UE side. He found that the challenges were not fully evident in the presentation, and more detailed plans for webinars and the expertise of the 3rd party experimenters were needed to attract broader attention and have a broader impact as a project.

Francisco Blanquer provided a vertical perspective, stating that the platform to manage the applications has to be technology-transparent due to the complexity for the use case developers. He also mentioned that the messages should be clearer to a broader audience, especially business people with a low technical profile.

6 D&C Goals for the rest of the Project

As the project moves forward and the use cases are developed, the VITAL-5G consortium has set some goals concerning scientific publications, participation in scientific conferences and workshops as well as T&L industry related events. This section describes the envisioned plan. We would like to note that when the sites are open to 3rd party experimenters, we expect an increase in both scientific peer-review publications and participation in conferences as new collaborations are going to be forged.

VITAL-5G will focus on participating in events and publishing in journals that cover the novel concepts of the project namely, automated vessel transport, 5G-enabled Network Applications development and validation, 5G orchestration tools for T&L virtualised applications and 5G testbeds and edge computing in T&L pilot sites.

6.1 Scientific Peer-Review Publications

Concerning the future plans for publishing in high-impact peer-reviewed journals, we have identified the following:

- IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology (IEEE TVT): <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=25>
- IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management (IEEE TNSM): <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=4275028>
- Applied Sciences: <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/applsci>
- IEEE Industry Applications Magazine: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=2943>
- IEEE Open Journal of Industry Applications: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=8782707>
- IEEE Open Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=8784355>
- IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=7274857>
- IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=25>
- IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=4275028>
- EURO Journal on Transportation and Logistics: <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/euro-journal-on-transportation-and-logistics>
- Sensors: <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sensors>
- Future Internet: <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/futureinternet>
- International Conference on European Integration - Realities and Perspectives (EIRP) proceedings: <https://dp.univ-danubius.ro/index.php/EIRP/index>

We envision to target at least 2 journal papers per site facility within the next year (mid-2023) which will give the project a minimum of six publications.

The papers will mainly target the areas of:

- IoT sensing over 5G in the T&L sector
- Network Application validation techniques
- Applications and services based on Network Application composition in B5G for the T&L sector
- Green Economy and Sustainable development
- AI/ML-enhanced mechanisms for autonomous vessel navigation
- Design, deployment, and evaluation of 5G-enabled Network Applications for T&L and automotive services
- Automated orchestration of 5G-enabled Network Applications

- The T&L-tailored design and deployment of 5G-enabled testbeds using 5G SA and edge computing
- Monitoring of 5G infrastructure and 5G Network Applications

6.2 Scientific conferences and workshops

Concerning the participation of members of the consortium in scientific conferences and workshops, through the expertise of the partners we have identified the following future events:

- IEEE Global Communications Conference (IEEE Globecom) 2023
- IEEE European Conference on Networks and Communications (IEEE EuCNC) 2023
- IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications (IEEE INFOCOM) 2023
- IEEE Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC) 2023
- ACM International Conference On Mobile Computing and Networking (ACM Mobicom) 2023 (Winter deadline)
- IEEE Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC) 2023
- IEEE 28th International Symposium for Design and Technology in Electronic Packaging (SIITME 2022)
- Jubilee 30th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR 2022)
- Transport Research Arena Conference (TRA 2023)
- European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ECAI 2023)
- IEEE International Black Sea Conference on Communications and Networking (IEEE BlackSeaCom 2023)
- International Conference on Communications (COMM 2024)
- International Conference on the Internet of Things (IOT 2024)
- International Conference on European Integration - Realities and Perspectives (EIRP 2023)

Participation in these events will also mean the publication of conference and demo papers, some of which are already in progress such as in the case of the IEEE Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC) 2023. In many of these conferences, there will be joint participations by members of the consortium generating more impactful papers and disseminating the project and its outcomes to larger audiences.

6.3 T&L expos and conferences

As shown in Table 10, the project moving forward will target 5G and continue presenting the project outcomes to stakeholders that would in turn increase the exploitability of the end produces and attracting more 3rd party experimenters when resources become available.

Table 10: T&L related expos and conferences that VITAL-5G partners will be able to disseminate the project effectively.

Exhibition	Location	Website
Logistics & Automation 2022	Madrid, Spain	https://www.logisticsmadrid.com/en/
Logistik & Transport	Gothenburg, Sweden	https://en.logistik.to/
Hypermotion	Frankfurt, Germany	https://hypermotion-frankfurt.messefrankfurt.com/frankfurt/en.html
Transport Logistic China 2022	Shanghai, China	https://www.transportlogistic-china.com/
Transport Logistic 2023	Munich, Germany	https://www.transportlogistic.de/en/
Leaders in Logistics Summit	London, United Kingdom	https://marketforcelive.com/leaders-in-logistics/

7 Conclusions

This report builds upon the deliverable D6.2 – “Dissemination and Communication activities v1.0” and reports on the period between M6 – M18 (June 2021 – June 2022). During this period, VITAL-5G participated to and organized a significant number of outreach activities. Through its active participation in high-level conferences and industry events, the project produced several publications and liaised with a number of different projects in the T&L ecosystem, solidifying its position amongst ICT-41 projects and breeding the ground for future collaborations from M18 onwards.

The social media and webpage, which serve as important tools for dissemination of the project’s results are thriving and the project will be able to use them more effectively to gain additional spotlight and interest of its target audiences.

The project, in its effort to engage 3rd party experimenters, will organize a workshop that will serve as a prelude to the Hackathon in order to prepare the participants on how to pitch their Network Application/product and provide some helpful resources. This will also serve as an engagement and retainment tactic of the participants and will benefit from word-to-mouth thus attracting more participants in the Hackathon envisioned for Spring 2023.

Even though the project is lacking in some metrics in relation to its time progression, we are confident that we can pick up the pace and achieve the KPIs set. More specifically, regarding the journal publications, the reports and subsequent scientific publications will increase as more tangible results will be produced. As for the video views, with the organization of more online trainings and proper dissemination, we are confident that we will reach the 1000 views before the end of the project. The same applies with the organization of training events. One is already under preparation for July 2022 and as we near closer towards the opening of the platform to 3rd party experimenters, we plan to have a series of events which will increase the impact of VITAL-5G.

The first meeting of the newly recruited External Advisory Board that took place on March 14th 2022 was also a success and we are confident that the project will receive the best directions for achieving maximum impact and multiply its outreach potential to the various stakeholders identified.

Finally, the plan for the D&C actions for the period between M18-M36 was discussed which will lead the project reaching and overshooting the KPIs set in previous deliverables.